

Calibration protocol

The FAAM TEi43i analyser was calibrated at FAAM on 22/5/2025 and 4/12/2025, by dynamically diluting FAAM's BOC HiQ SO₂ in air surveillance standard in synthetic 'zero' air.

The analyser was also calibrated on 11/9/2025 at the [COZI laboratory](#), Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories, University of York, by dynamically diluting two BOC HiQ alpha-volumetric SO₂ in N₂ standards in scrubbed ambient air.

Date and staff	Location	BOC SO ₂ standard material and cylinder numbers, mole fraction (nmol/mol) and uncertainty	Dilution gas	Dynamic dilution equipment
22/5/2025 SBau and MB	On board FAAM aircraft	154578-AK-S (40 litres) Cyl # 133668SG 1030 ± 5% SO ₂ in air	Synthetic air, BOC material number 122944-L-C, BTCA-178 grade	FAAM 'JADE' See Note 1
9/11/2025 JS, PL, SBau	COZI laboratory	167163-AV-S (10 litres) Cyl # 251500SG 579 ± 5% SO ₂ in N ₂	Pure air generated (Eco Physics model PAG003)	FAAM/COZI See Note 2
9/11/2025 JS, PL, SBau	COZI laboratory	150620-AH-S (5 litres) Cyl # 178671SG 5100 ± 5% SO ₂ in N ₂	Pure air generated (Eco Physics model PAG003)	FAAM/COZI
4/12/2025 JS and SBau	FAAM Labs	154578-AK-S (40 litres) Cyl # 133668SG 1030 ± 5% SO ₂ in air	Synthetic air, BOC material number 122944-L-C, BTCA-178	FAAM 'JADE'

Note 1: The FAAM 'JADE' dynamic dilution system consists of two Alicat Scientific mass flow controllers (MFC) part numbers MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON (s/n 60935) for dilution air, and

MCS-500SCCM-D-I-VITON (s/n 226744) for air or nitrogen. Both MFCs are set by an NI LabVIEW software to program the required diluted mole fraction.

The diluted SO₂ mole fraction is calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{SO}_2 \text{ mole fraction} &= y && \text{[ppb]} \\
 \text{SO}_2 \text{ MFC} &= a && \text{[sccm]} \quad // \text{ full scale is 500 sccm} \\
 \text{BOC cyl mole fraction} &= b && \text{[ppb]} \\
 \text{ZA MFC} &= c && \text{[sccm]} \quad // \text{ full scale is 5000 sccm} \\
 y &= \frac{a \times b}{a + c}
 \end{aligned}$$

The uncertainty of the diluted mole fraction y can be calculated as:

$$\Delta y^2 = \left(\frac{\delta y}{\delta a} \times \Delta a \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta y}{\delta b} \times \Delta b \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta y}{\delta c} \times \Delta c \right)^2$$

Where:

$$\frac{\delta y}{\delta a} = \frac{b \times c}{(a + c)^2}$$

$$\frac{\delta y}{\delta b} = \frac{a}{a + c}$$

$$\frac{\delta y}{\delta c} = - \frac{a \times b}{(a + c)^2}$$

$$\Delta a = \pm 0.6\% \text{ of reading or } \pm 0.1\% \text{ of full scale}, \text{ whichever is greater [sccm]}$$

$$\Delta b = \pm 5\% \text{ [expressed in ppb]}$$

$$\Delta c = \pm (0.8\% \text{ of reading} + 0.2\% \text{ of full scale}) \text{ [sccm]}$$

Note 2: The FAAM/COZI dynamic dilution system employed the FAAM 'JADE' MFC model MCS-5SLPM-D-I-VITON (s/n 60935) for delivering the SO₂/N₂ standard, with a rated accuracy

$$\Delta a = \pm (0.8\% \text{ of reading} + 0.2\% \text{ of full scale}) \text{ [sccm]},$$

and a Bronkhorst MFC model F-202AV-M10-XAD-22-V (s/n M25207747A), 100.0 l/min full scale, for dilution air, with a rated accuracy

$$\Delta c = \pm (0.5\% \text{ of reading} + 0.1\% \text{ of full scale}) \text{ [l/min]}$$

The Bronkhorst MFC is calibrated for *normal* T & P (0.00°C and 1013.25 hPa(a)), whereas the Alicat Scientific MFC is calibrated for *standard* T & P (25.0°C, 14.69 PSIA or 1013.25 hPa(a)). The l/min mass flow rate was converted to sccm, using equation

$$sccm = \frac{ln/min \times 1000 \times 298}{273}$$

Pressurised dilution 'zero' air was supplied to the Bronkhorst MFC by an Eco Physics Pure Air Generator.

Calibration results

The following multi-point linearisation plots were analysed using orthogonal distance regression fit to obtain the sensitivity (slope) and its 2σ uncertainty.

Results for the 4/12/2025 calibration

Date, Location	Range, ppb	Sensitivity, ppb/ppb
22/05/2025, FAAM	0-200	1.15 ± 0.05
11/09/2025, COZI	0-150	1.14 ± 0.12
11/09/2025, COZI	0-550	1.20 ± 0.16
4/12/2025, FAAM	0-200	1.14 ± 0.01
		Mean = 1.16

All sensitivity slopes agree within their 2σ uncertainties. The mean sensitivity used to scale SO₂ mole fractions is taken as 1.16.

Calibration certificates

Certificate

A Member of The Linde Group

BOC Limited
The Priestley Centre, 10 Priestley Road
The Surrey Research Park, Guildford GU2 7XY
www.BOConline.co.uk

Orders and technical enquiries
Tel 0800 02 0800
Fax 0800 136 601
specialproducts@boc.com

From outside of the UK
Tel +44 1483 244 067
Fax +44 1483 532 115

COMPONENT

SULPHUR DIOXIDE
SYNTHETIC AIR

NOMINAL COMPOSITION CERTIFIED VALUE

1 PPM = 1.03 PPM
BAL

CERTIFICATE NO.: 21/001085
CERTIFICATE DATE: 13 JAN 2021 **USE BY:** 12 JAN 2026
APPROVED SIGNATORY Sofiane Hadjilah

PROD ORDER	BARCODE NUMBER	CYLINDER NO.	MATERIAL	PAGE
2789073	21901310019969	133668SG	154578-AK-S	1 of 2

BOC001/5390/0418

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Fax +44 1483 532 115

To reorder, please quote 154578 AK SPECTRA-SEAL CERTIFIED

CYLINDER DETAILS :

Cylinder Size: AK 40.00 Litres Valve outlet: BS14
Nominal cylinder contents: 200.0 Bar(g) at 15°C

Certified values have an uncertainty of $\leq 5\%$, and have been determined using standards traceable to internationally recognised reference materials, or relevant ISO standards.

STABILITY ASSURED until the use by date.

Composition is expressed on a molar basis unless otherwise specified.

Do not use below 5% of actual contents.

Store and use between -5° & 50°C unless otherwise specified.

BOC supplies a full range of gas control equipment to suit all applications.

Is your regulator fit for purpose?

- A precision gas from BOC requires a precision regulator
- The BCGA recommends you maintain or replace your equipment every 5 years

Call 0800 02 0800 for more information

PROD ORDER	BARCODE NUMBER	CYLINDER NO.	MATERIAL
2789073	21901310019969	133668SG	154578-AK-S

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2 of 2

BOC001/5390/0418

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Forge, 43 Church Street West, Woking, Surrey, GU21 6HT
www.boconline.co.uk

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Tel 0800 02 0800
specialproducts@boc.com

COMPONENT	NOMINAL COMPOSITION	CERTIFIED VALUE
SULPHUR DIOXIDE	500 PPB	= 579 PPB
NITROGEN	BAL	

CERTIFICATE NO.: 23/000397
CERTIFICATE DATE: 06 JAN 2023 USE BY: 05 JAN 2028
APPROVED SIGNATORY Frederick Evans

F.E

PROD ORDER BARCODE NUMBER CYLINDER NO. MATERIAL
2852736 21901300164112 251500SG 167163-AV-S

PAGE
1 of 2

990001/5396/CS1/0122

To reorder, please quote 167163 AV SPECTRA-SEAL CERTIFIED

CYLINDER DETAILS :

Cylinder Size: AV 10.00 Litres Valve outlet: BS14
Nominal cylinder contents: 200.0 Bar(g) at 15°C

Certified values have an uncertainty of $\leq 5\%$, and have been determined using standards traceable to internationally recognised reference materials, or relevant ISO standards.

STABILITY ASSURED until the use by date.

Composition is expressed on a molar basis unless otherwise specified.

Do not use below 5% of actual contents.
Store and use between -5° & 50°C unless otherwise specified.

This product conforms to the following specification:

All concentrations are MOLE fractions

BOC supplies a full range of gas control equipment to suit all applications.

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- The BCGA recommends you maintain or replace your equipment every 5 years

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PROD ORDER	BARCODE NUMBER	CYLINDER NO.	MATERIAL
2852736	21901300164112	251500SG	167163-AV-S

Certificate

BOC Limited
Forge, 43 Church Street West, Woking, Surrey, GU21 6HT
www.boconline.co.uk

Orders and technical enquiries
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COMPONENT

SULPHUR DIOXIDE
NITROGEN

NOMINAL COMPOSITION CERTIFIED VALUE

5 PPM = 5.10 PPM
BAL

HiO[®]

CERTIFICATE NO.: 25/010246
CERTIFICATE DATE: 01 MAY 2025 USE BY: 30 APR 2030
APPROVED SIGNATORY Sofiane Hadjilah

SH

PROD ORDER 2920330
BARCODE NUMBER 21901520038958
CYLINDER NO. 178671SG
MATERIAL 150620-AH-S

PAGE
1 of 2

BOC001/5390/EST/0122

George, 45 Church Street West, Woking, Surrey, GU21 6HT
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Orders and technical enquiries
Tel 0800 02 0800
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To reorder, please quote 150620 AH SPECTRA-SEAL CERTIFIED

CYLINDER DETAILS :

Cylinder Size: AH 5.00 Litres Valve outlet: BS14
Nominal cylinder contents: 200.0 Bar(g) at 15°C

Certified values have an uncertainty of $\leq 5\%$, and have been determined using standards traceable to internationally recognised reference materials, or relevant ISO standards.

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2920330	21901520038958	178671SG	150620-AH-S